

Extended Value Chain Analysis for [value chain] in [country]

Prepared by [Surname Initial, ...]

Version [1.0], [Month Year]

This document forms the basis for the Extended Value Chain Analysis (EVCA) (Task 4.3) and will be used in relation to, both, the Desktop Review (Stage 1) starting in November 2021 and Interviews (Stage 2) starting in January 2022. The template should be completed before starting workshops in April-May 2022.

Please refer back to 'Methodological Guidelines for WP4' document for further information on principles, dimensions, and steps involved in the EVCA.

Partners should complete a **separate version of this document for each value chain** (VC) identified in [Deliverable 4.2](#).

BEFORE STARTING DATA COLLECTION all partners should produce a one-page summary and initial diagram representing the key features and significance of the focal VC in the context of the MRL. This will provide a starting point for data collection, in terms of identifying gaps, and supplementing and verifying what you already know (including information in other work pages and deliverables). The initial summary section has been shared as a separate document and the information should later be copied into Section 1.1 of this template.

Initial summaries should be completed by Monday 6th December for discussion at the WP4 Drop-in session on Thursday 9th December 2021. Please upload initial diagrams and one-page summaries should be uploaded on the VRE here:

****4. WP4 >Task 4.3 Extended Value Chain Analysis >Stage 1- Desktop Review****

Information collected in earlier deliverables and work packages (e.g., D2.2, D3.3, D4.1, D4.2) can be used as a starting point for filling in this document

Always work on the principle that it is expedient to reuse data!

Space is provided in each section to record information; please expand this space to the length necessary to describe your VC. The document may become very long, so please refresh and make use of the table of contents and list of tables for ease of navigating the document.

Aim of this document

To generate an overview of the current performance of the VC in the MRL(i), its interactions with other VC(s) in the MRL (ii), and to what extent it is tele-coupled (iii).

In the desktop review stage, use existing material (secondary sources), including descriptive statistics, where available, to provide a factual basis for understanding the VC performance.

Information collected in earlier deliverables (D2.2, D4.1, D4.2) can be used as a starting point for filling in this document **Always work on the principle that it is expedient to reuse data!**

In the next stage (January-March 2022), interviews will be conducted to fill in information not available via secondary sources and to explore perceptions and preferences of specific local actors in the MRL that may not be captured in published material. Further guidance for Stage 2 will be provided in due course.

It is important to note sources (published review, expert opinion) and, where relevant, provide comment on the reliabilities of sources being used.

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List of acronyms

EVCA	Extended Value Chain Analysis
FTE	Full Time Equivalent
LUS	Land Use System
MRL	Mountain Reference Landscape
MRR	Mountain Reference Region
MS	Member State
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
VC	Value Chain

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1. Step 1: Narrative summary

As an initial step, and final step, please provide a narrative summary of your focal value chain identified in [Deliverable 4.2](#).

This is an important step to ensure that partners are clear about the key features and significance of their focal value chain for the purposes of data collection and reporting.

1.1. Initial summary

BEFORE STARTING DATA COLLECTION please draw on your existing knowledge of your focal value chain (including information gathered for earlier deliverables and tasks) to describe your focal value chain in terms of key elements of:

- Territorial capital;
- Practices that characterise the main stages of the value chain (production, processing, distribution and marketing, consumption);
- Types of Actors involved;
- Environmental, soci-cultural and economic values generated at different stages of the chain;
- Enabling environment (infrastructure or governance) and
- Key outcomes (has territorial capital been increased or decreased) in the context of the MRL

An important question to have in mind when writing this initial summary is: ***'what is the point?'*** Recognising that different elements are more or less important in different value chains is important in developing this summary and ensuring that partners focus on important aspects and indicators to assess performance when completing the remainder of this document.

a) **Please use the space below to provide your initial summary** (*max 1 page of text*):

<p><u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u></p>

1.2. Final summary

After completing data collection (desktop and interview stages) please provide an updated summary of your focal value chain. This should match your final iteration of the VC diagram

- a) **Please use the space below to provide your final summary** (*max. 1 page of text*):

<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>

2. Focal VC Analysis

Information to be recorded in this section relates directly to the focal value chain identified in [Deliverable 4.2](#).

2.1. Step 2 – Describe the general context

- a) **What are the main types of territorial capital available in the Mountain Reference Landscape (MRL)?** *Think about different forms of capital (economic, socio-cultural and environmental)*

<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>

b) **What are the main sustainable rural development issues present in the MRL?**

Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section

2.2. Step 3 – Describe the history and trends

a) **What are the final product(s) associated with the VC?** *Think about the different value propositions associated with the product and also include information about different categories of the final product (for example, premium or discount varieties)*

Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section

b) **How long has this VC existed in the MRL?** *Also think about whether this VC typical in the context of the wider MRR and/or Member State (MS)?*

<p><u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u></p>

c) **What are the trends in demand for the VC product(s)?** *Think about past, current, and future demand. Also consider where the demand exists (e.g., local (MRL), regional (MRR), domestic (MS), international...) and any significant differences in types of consumers for the VC products*

<p><u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u></p>

d) **What is the nature of competition for the VC products?** *Think about how alternative/substitute products in the MRL influence demand, as well as competition from outside of the MRL.*

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Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section

2.3. Step 4 – Describe the structure of the VC

2.3.1. Practices

Each practice represents a stage in the VC, moving through the following typology:

Production >> Processing >> Distribution & marketing >> Consumption.

a) Please note all the relevant practices at each stage of your focal VC using Table 1.

Table 1: List of practices in the focal VC by type

Practice type	List of Practices
<p><u>Production</u></p> <p><i>Think about all the practices involved in <u>production of commodities</u> on which the final product(s) are based.</i></p>	-
<p><u>Processing</u></p> <p><i>Think about all the activities which involve <u>transformation of commodities</u> into the final product(s).</i></p>	-
<p><u>Distribution and Marketing</u></p>	-

<i>Think about practices relevant to <u>how the product is provided to the consumer.</u></i>	
<u>Consumption</u> <i>Think about practices relevant to <u>consumption of the end product(s).</u></i>	-
<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>	

b) **How are the practices identified above assembled into the focal value chain?** *Think about the sequence of practices and note the connections (this will help in developing the VC diagram, and vice versa)*

Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section

c) **What are the individual attitudes and habits that shape these practices?** *Interviews will be helpful in answering this question, but also consider previous research, etc.*

<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>

d) **What relationships and collaborations are there that shape these practices?** *Interviews will be helpful in answering this question, but also consider previous research, etc.*

<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>

e) **What are the main knowledge ('know-what' and 'know-how') and skills used in VC practices?** *Think about each practice type (production, processing, distribution/marketing, consumption).*

<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>

f) Please note which elements of territorial capital enter your focal VC at each stage using Table 2.

Table 2: Territorial capital entering the VC at different practice stages

Practice stage	Territorial capitals entering the VC
<u>Production</u>	-
<u>Processing</u>	-
<u>Distribution and Marketing</u>	-
<u>Consumption</u>	-
<p><u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u></p>	

g) Have the practices in your focal VC been adapted to suit the territorial capital specific to your MRL? If so, in what ways? How does this affect the way your focal VC behaves compared to other areas?

Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section

****To help with the WP5 clustering, please also consider the following questions on the topic of innovation****

- h) **Are there examples of innovation in practices within your focal VC?** Consider the following questions (I – VIII), noting your answers in the space/tables provided:
- I. **Are there examples of new¹ final products (or inputs for the next stage) being produced?** (Note in Table 3)
 - II. **Are there new by-products being produced? – and what VCs do they enter?** (Note in Table 3)

Table 3: New products and by-products produced at different VC stages

	New products	New by-products <i>(also noting which VCs they enter)</i>
<u>Production</u>		
<u>Processing</u>		
<u>Distribution & Marketing</u>		
<u>Consumption</u>		
<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>		

- III. **Using Table 4, please note new processing techniques being used – and their associated motivation** (e.g. to reduce environmental footprint, to reduce economic costs, other?)

¹ New means was not typical practice for this VC stage in the previous decade.

Table 4: New processing techniques in VC

New processing techniques	Motivation
<p><u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u></p>	

- IV. **Using Table 5, please note new marketing or distribution approaches being used – and their associated motivation (e.g. to reduce environmental footprint, to reduce economic costs, other?)**

Table 5: New marketing and distribution techniques in VC

New marketing or distribution approaches	Motivation
<p><u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u></p>	

- V. **Please note what form of digital technologies are used in each stage of the VC using Table 6 (e.g., e-commerce)**

Table 6: Digital technologies used in different VC stages

	Digital technologies
<u>Production</u>	-
<u>Processing</u>	-
<u>Distribution & Marketing</u>	-
<u>Consumption</u>	-
<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>	

VI. **Are there any other innovations in your focal VC not covered above?**

Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section

VII. **Check Annex 4 (D11 – 21) for information about the region’s performance using patents and other indicators of innovations, and comment on how these might be relevant to the VC in your case.**

<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>

VIII. **What do the innovations identified mean for the performance of your focal VC?**

<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>

****To help with the WP5 clustering, please also consider the following questions relating to the governance structure of the overall VC****

- i) **Which of the following definitions best fits the MRL VC? (And explain why)²:**
- **Market** (*low complexity of transactions³, high ability to codify transactions, high supply base capability, low power asymmetry*)
 - **Modular** (*high complexity of transactions, high ability to codify transactions, high supply base capability, medium power asymmetry*)
 - **Relational** (*high complexity of transactions, low ability to codify transactions, high supply base capability, medium power asymmetry*)
 - **Captive** (*high complexity of transactions, high ability to codify transactions, low supply base capability, medium to high power asymmetry*)

² Optional: consider D22 – 25 and D30 in Annex 4 as sources to benchmark the VC governance typology with broader regional trends.

³ Transactions are the exchange practices (monetary or otherwise) involved in a trade between a buyer and seller.

- **Hierarchy** (*high complexity of transactions, low ability to codify transactions, low supply base capability, high power asymmetry*)

<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>

- j) **Have there been innovations in how the VC is governed?** (*e.g., new cooperative processes; new participatory or democratic institutions developed; new knowledge collaborations*)

<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>

- k) **What do these VC governance structures mean for the performance of the VC?**

<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>

2.3.2. Actors

Actors in the VC should be listed based on the following typology:

Land-Use System (LUS) manager⁴; Non-Governmental Organisation (NGO); civil society; broker/advisor; business (agri); business (non-agri); public sector; research; other.

The categories in this typology are not necessarily mutually exclusive and partners should be guided by the main expertise and interests of the actor in the context of the focal VC. It also may be possible for the same actor(s) be involved in more than one practice in the VC (e.g., production and processing), therefore should be noted in relation to each relevant type.

a) Please note all the actors involved in your focal VC using Table 7:

Table 7: List of actors in the focal VC by type

Actor type	List of actors
<p><u>Land-Use System (LUS) manager</u></p> <p><i>Think about all the actors that manage land that generates inputs or is used for producing commodities for processing in the focal VC.</i></p>	-
<p><u>NGO</u></p> <p><i>Think about all the actors that work in Non-Governmental Organisations that are involved in the focal VC or enabling environment (they may own land, implement projects, or provide training)</i></p>	-
<p><u>Civil society</u></p> <p><i>Think about all the non-organised actors that may be involved in the focal VC or</i></p>	-

⁴ Formerly referred to as 'producer' (LUS manager reflecting this as a broader category)

<p><i>the enabling environment as citizens or activists.</i></p>	
<p><u>Broker/advisor</u></p> <p><i>Think about actors such as innovation brokers, extension officers, business advisors that engage directly in the focal VC.</i></p>	-
<p><u>Business (agri)</u></p> <p><i>Think about all the actors in businesses either on-farm or beyond the farmgate (but still agricultural) that are involved in focal VC.</i></p>	-
<p><u>Business (non-agri)</u></p> <p><i>Think about all the actors that are either non-agricultural businesses or diversified (non-agri) on-farm enterprises within the focal VC.</i></p>	-
<p><u>Public sector</u></p> <p><i>Think about all the actors that exist as public authorities or have policy-making responsibilities affecting the focal VC.</i></p>	-
<p><u>Research</u></p> <p><i>Think about all the actors involved in research affecting the focal VC.</i></p>	-
<p><u>Other</u></p> <p><i>Think about other actors involved in the focal VC that don't fit well within any of the types listed above.</i></p>	-

- b) **How many, and in what proportion, are actors in the focal value chain distributed in terms of the characteristics noted in Table 8? Please note, exact figures are not required – instead record orders of magnitude and include any further commentary to support understanding.**

Table 8: Numbers and key characteristics of actors involved in the focal VC

Practice type	Number of actors	Distribution of gendered roles <i>(Male, female, other)</i>	Participation of Young people <i>(<25, 25-40, >40)</i>	Ethnic origin	'Incomers' to the MRL
<u>Production</u>					
<u>Processing</u>					
<u>Distribution & Marketing</u>					
<u>Consumption</u>					
<u>Space to include any further commentary relating to actor characteristics</u>					
<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>					

- c) **For each actor type in the VC, consider trends in business models according to the typologies representing columns in Table 9. Please note any exceptions or outliers to the main trends as appropriate.**

Table 9: Business model trends by actor type in the focal VC

Actor type	Size⁵ <i>(Small, medium, large)</i>	Business structure/ ownership⁶ <i>(Sole proprietor, cooperative, partnership, LLC, corporation)</i>	Market orientation <i>(For profit, not-for-profit)</i>	Level of technological innovation/uptake <i>(Low, average, advanced)</i>
<u>LUS manager</u>				
<u>NGO</u>				
<u>Civil society</u>				
<u>Broker/advisor</u>				
<u>Business (agri)</u>				
<u>Business (non-agri)</u>				
<u>Public sector</u>				
<u>Research</u>				
<u>Other</u>				
<u>Please use this space to record information on exceptions and outliers to the main trends characterising each actor type</u>				
<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>				

⁵ Small = fewer than 50 persons; Medium = fewer than 250 employees; Large = higher than figures for medium.

⁶ <https://www.g2.com/articles/types-of-business-ownership>

2.3.3. Flows

In this section we are interested in VC inputs and outputs – we refer to these **outputs-inputs as the ‘flows’ in the VC**, which move between stages, enter (in the form of territorial capital) and leave the chain (in the form of by-products or externalities⁷), and eventually become the final product. These can be in tangible and intangible forms, including:

- Physical materials/products (e.g. grain, milk, pollutants)
- Information and meaning (e.g. knowledge passed between actors, branding)

It is also useful to note whether flows can be categorised as private, club, common-pool or public goods.⁸

It is helpful to visualise the VC process to identify flows, therefore it is expected that this section will be completed in association with the VC diagram template provided in Annex 2 to the T4.3 Guidance.

Please use Table 10 to note flows entering and leaving each stage in the focal VC.

Table 10: Flows entering, within, and leaving the focal VC at each practice stage

Practice stage	Territorial capital entering the VC	Flows that pass to the next practice stage	By-products and externalities that leave the VC
<i>For each flow please note in brackets whether they can be categorised as private, club, common-pool or public good (see footnote 7)</i>			
<u>Production</u>			
<u>Processing</u>			
<u>Distribution & Marketing</u>			
<u>Consumption</u>			
<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>			

⁷ Externalities (e.g. pollination of surrounding crops by bees kept for honey), By-products (e.g. ‘draff’ residue produced in brewing process, which can be used as livestock feed).

⁸ <https://quickeconomics.com/different-types-of-goods/>

2.3.4. Valorisation and outcomes

The purpose of this section is to consider how value is added by actors within each practice stage – we think of these in terms of economic, socio-cultural, and environmental valorisation, and therefore include, both, market and non-market values.

Please refer to the WP4 methodological guidance (Section 3.3.4) document to see more detail regarding the types of information you may be able to collect in relation to each stage. Please include figures where available.

- a) Please consider the range of indicators in Table 11 to assess how **economic value** is accrued in your focal VC

Table 11: Economic valorisation within the focal VC

	Primary Sector	Secondary	Tertiary	Overall (all sectors)
<u>MRL employment rate</u>				
<i>Is VC employment rate higher or lower than MRL average?</i>				
	Production	Processing	Distribution & Marketing	Consumption
<u>VC Employment</u> <i>Estimated total FTEs employed in MRL VC at each stage</i> <i>(<25 FTE, 25-50; 51-100; >100)</i>				
<u>Built capital</u> <i>What built capital is required for the practices at each stage ?</i> <i>(also note any changes in investment)</i>				
<u>Total Market Values</u> ⁹ <i>(note spatial unit of analysis)</i>				

⁹ These values may vary a lot depending on the different markets. Please give the range if this is the case.

<p><i>Proportion of total Market Value added at each stage</i></p> <p><i>(<25%, 25-50% 51-75% >75%)</i></p>				
<p><u>Average wage</u></p> <p><i>Please note for each VC stage, plus whether this is above or below the national minimum or living wage</i></p>				
<p><u>Employers</u></p> <p><i>Who are the main actors employing people or investing at each stage ?</i></p>				
<p><u>Livelihood viability</u></p> <p><i>Provide a short narrative on whether livelihoods are viable in the MRL at each stage of the VC</i></p>				
<p>*The following questions are optional*</p>				
<p><u>Net income</u></p> <p><i>Net income of each MRL actor p.a. (or return on turnover, return on investment)</i></p> <p><i>Productivity of MRL FTE labour per hour</i></p>				
	Production	Processing	Distribution & marketing	Consumption
<p><u>Taxes</u></p> <p><i>What taxes are paid by actors at various stages? (Add amounts if possible)</i></p>				
<p><u>Grants and subsidies</u></p> <p><i>What subsidies and grants received by actors</i></p>				

at various stages? (Add amounts if possible)				
<p><u>Contribution to GDP</u></p> <p>Starting from the National VC value-added contribution to GDP and to balance of trade, what proportion of this national contribution comes from the MRL?</p> <p>(<25%, 25-50% 51-75% >75%)</p>				
<p><u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u></p>				

b) How do the economic values expressed in Table 11 (above) relate to the averages for the MRR or Member State (benchmarking)? (See Annex 4 of the Guidance document)

Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section

c) Within the MRL, how has the economic capital base changed by the end of the VC? (Consider whether it has increased, decreased or stayed the same, and provide a short explanation)

<p>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</p>
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d) Please consider the range of indicators in Table 12 to assess how socio-cultural value is accrued in different stages of your focal VC

Table 12: Socio-cultural valorisation within the focal VC

	Production	Processing	Distribution & Marketing	Consumption
<p><u>Access to natural resources</u></p> <p><i>How does the VC enable or constrain access</i></p>				
<p><u>Is the resource system accessible to local entrepreneurs?</u></p> <p>- Highly accessible (low entrance costs) - Medium - Highly inaccessible (high entrance costs)</p>				
<p><u>Education/training</u></p> <p><i>Indicate the level generally required at each stage: school leaver, further education, university first degree, master's or above</i></p> <p><i>*Optional: How does this benchmark to national figures for skills/training? – See Annex 4 D39 and D40*</i></p>				

<p><u>Trust/cooperation between actors</u></p> <p><i>(High, Medium, Low)</i></p>				
<p><u>Sharing between actors</u></p> <p><i>Information and material (e.g., machinery or labour)</i></p> <p><i>(High, Medium, Low)</i></p>				
<p><u>Local participation in decision making</u></p> <p><i>(High, Medium, Low)</i></p>				
<p><u>Local ownership of the assets and control of the finances</u></p> <p><i>(High, Medium, Low)</i></p>				
<p><u>Contribution of VC practices to existing cultural landscapes</u></p> <p><i>(High, Medium, Low)</i></p>				
<p><u>Contribution of tradition and customs in VC practices</u></p> <p><i>(High, Medium, Low)</i></p>				
<p><u>Contribution of symbolic capital</u></p> <p><i>VC dependence unique, or specific, to the reputation of the area?</i></p> <p><i>(High, Medium, Low)</i></p>				
<p><u>Deprivation</u></p> <p><i>Is MRL area subject to deprivation? (Poverty hotspot)</i></p>				
<p><u>Gendering</u></p>				

<p>Are occupations/actors in each VC stage : Majority male, majority female, or mixed</p> <p>Please also provide a short description</p>				
<p><u>Age profile</u></p> <p>Are occupations/actors in each VC stage : Majority <40; majority <60; majority > 60</p> <p>Please also provide a short description</p>				
<p><u>Immigration</u></p> <p>Do the practices or actors involve : Mostly local people, mixed, mostly immigrants</p> <p>Please also provide a short description including – whether immigrants are from different ethnic groups from the dominant local population</p>				
<p><u>Occupational hazards</u></p> <p>Note any key hazards associated with practices at each stage</p>				
<p><u>Physical and mental health</u></p> <p>Note how practices at each stage might lead to increased or decreased physical and mental health outcomes</p> <p>Also note whether there are overall positive health outcomes, mixed health</p>				

<p><i>outcomes, negative health outcomes</i></p>				
<p><u>Human-environmental impacts</u></p> <p><i>Note whether practices at any/each stage has an effect on potable water, food safety/nutrition, zoonotic pests, and diseases, and air quality</i></p> <p><i>Also note whether the effect is positive, mixed, or negative</i></p>				
<p><u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u></p>				

e) How do the socio-cultural values expressed in Table 12 (above) relate to the averages for the MRR or Member State (benchmarking)? (See Annex 4 of the Guidance document)

Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section

f) Within the MRL, how has the socio-cultural capital base changed by the end of the VC? (Consider whether it has increased, decreased or stayed the same, and provide a short explanation)

<p>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</p>
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g) Please consider the range of indicators in Table 13 to assess how environmental value is accrued in different stages of your focal VC

Table 13: Environmental valorisation within the focal VC

	Production	Processing	Distribution & Marketing	Consumption
<p><u>Natural resource inputs</u></p> <p><i>Consider the resources used at inputs at each VC stage (e.g. water - quantity and quality, soil fertility, air quality, rocks and minerals, wild flora, and fauna)</i></p>				
<p><u>Locality of natural resource inputs</u></p> <p><i>Proportion of natural resources local to the MRL</i></p> <p><i>(<25%, 25-50% 51-75% >75%)</i></p>				
<p><u>Sustainability of resource use</u></p> <p><i>Is the MRL natural resource based being used at a sustainable rate within each stage?</i></p>				
<p><u>Farmed resources</u></p> <p><i>Consider the resources used at each VC stage</i></p>				

<p>(e.g. arable crops, forestry, livestock)</p>				
<p><u>Locality of farmed resource inputs</u></p> <p><i>Proportion of farmed resources local to the MRL</i></p> <p>(<25%, 25-50% 51-75% >75%)</p>				
<p><u>Competition</u></p> <p><i>Is there competition for these natural and farmed resources from other VCs? (provide details)</i></p>				
<p><u>Pollution, erosion, and waste</u></p> <p><i>Note whether practices at any/each stage has an effect on soil erosion and pollution, air pollution, water pollution, waste that cannot be or is not reused</i></p>				
<p><u>Biodiversity and habitat quality</u></p> <p><i>Consider whether practices at any/each stage has negative, positive or mixed outcomes for biodiversity and/or habitat quality in the MRL?</i></p>				
<p><u>GHG emissions</u></p> <p><i>Consider the contribution that practices at each stage</i></p> <p><i>(Contribute to GHG emissions, GHG neutral, sequesters GHGs)</i></p>				
<p><u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u></p>				

h) How do the environmental values expressed in Table 13 (above) relate to the averages for the MRR or Member State (benchmarking)? *(See Annex D of the Guidance document)*

Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section

i) Within the MRL, how has the environmental capital base changed by the end of the VC? *(Consider whether it has increased, decreased or stayed the same, and provide a short explanation)*

Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section

j) What are the economic, socio-cultural, and environmental outcomes sought for your focal VC?

Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section

k) Are these outcomes sought by local VC actors within the MRL or a wider set of actors? (e.g. national society, all consumers)

Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section

3. Conducive Enabling Environment (Step 5)

This step involves analysis of the ‘conducive enabling environment’, which sets the conditions for the practices involved, and the rules/norms used by actors in the value chains. This includes aspects of governance and institutions that **support, but are not part of, the focal VC**.

Please complete tables for each practice stage of the VC; bear in mind that the same information (e.g., policies) may be included in tables for different stages, but interpreted based on the perspective of actors at each stage of the VC.

a) Please reflect on different elements of the conducive enabling environment supporting practices and actors at the production stage of the VC in Table 14.

Table 14: Conducive enabling environment relevant to the production stage of the focal VC

Infrastructure		Scale (MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)
<i>What physical infrastructure (including transport & energy) is available for practices at the production stage of the VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>What digital infrastructure is available for practices at the production stage of the VC ?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>Please note any key aspects relating to infrastructure in that are important to understanding the production stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>	-	
Strategies and vision		Scale (MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)
<i>What sectoral or VC-specific strategic plans or documents support actors and practices at the production stage of the focal VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>What territorial strategies or visions (e.g. green recovery) have a direct relationship on function and performance at the production stage of the focal VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>Please note any key aspects of these strategies and visions that are important to understanding the production stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>	-	
Projects and programmes		Scale

		(MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)
<i>What sectoral or VC-specific projects or programmes support actors and practices at the production stage of the focal VC ?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>What other territorial projects or programmes have a direct influence on the function and performance at the production stage of the focal VC ?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>Please note any key aspects of these projects and programmes that are important to understanding the production stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>	-	
Regulatory		Scale (MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)
<i>What key legal and 'soft law' requirements do VC practices at the production stage have to comply with? (Think about health and safety, climate and environmental standards, licencing, employment law, taxation, property rights, legal contracts, etc)</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>Please note any key aspects of these regulatory institutions that are important to understanding the production stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>	-	
Cooperation		Scale (MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)

<p><i>What formal collective action institutions exist that support the production stage of the VC?</i></p> <p><i>(Note, this does not include actors that are directly involved in the focal VC (included in actors section))</i></p>	-	-
<p><i>Please note any key aspects of these collective action institutions that are important to understanding the production stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i></p>		
	Finance	Scale <i>(MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)</i>
<p><i>How are practices at the production stage of the VC financed?</i></p>	-	
<p><i>Is access to capital and revenue a problem for actors at the production stage of the VC?</i></p> <p><i>(If yes, please specify how)</i></p>	-	
<p><i>Is the production stage of the VC associated with any 'new' private sector investment ?</i></p> <p><i>(Think about payment for eco-system services, carbon credits, etc)</i></p>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<p><i>What public subsidies or incentives are available to support actors and practices at the production stage of the VC?</i></p>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<p><i>What taxes or other levies are relevant to practices at the production stage of the VC?</i></p>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<p><i>What other fiscal charges (interest rates, exchange rates) impact on the production stage of the VC?</i></p>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<p><i>In what ways does the land market and price of land impact on the production stage of the VC?</i></p>	-	

<i>Please note any key aspects of these financial institutions that are important to understanding the production stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>	-	
Certification processes		Scale (MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)
<i>What regional and/or quality assurance processes are relevant to the production stage of the VC? (Include, PDO, PGI, etc.)</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>What other certification processes are relevant to the production stage of the VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>Please note any key aspects of these certification institutions that are important to understanding the production stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>	-	
Knowledge, advice and skills *Note informal knowledge sharing between VC actors is included in SC valorisation*		Scale (MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)
<i>What specific training and skills provision is available for practices at the production stage of the VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>What knowledge advisors are available to support practices at the production stage of the VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>Please note any key aspects of these certification institutions that are important to understanding the production stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>	-	
Market structure		Scale

	Practice¹⁰	Market structure¹¹	Power relations¹²	<i>(MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)</i>
<i>How would you describe the market structure and power relations within it for each practice at the production stage of the VC process? (Please use the typologies outlined in footnotes)</i>				-
				-
				-
<i>Please note any key aspects relating to market structure institutions that are important to understanding the production stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>	-			-
<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this table</u>				

b) Please reflect on different elements of the conducive enabling environment supporting practices and actors at the processing stage of the VC in table 15.

Table 15: Conducive enabling environment relevant to the processing stage of the focal VC

	Infrastructure	Scale <i>(MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)</i>
<i>What physical infrastructure (including transport & energy) is available for practices at the processing stage of the VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
	-	-

¹⁰ This refers to different practices within the production stage (identified in Table 1)

¹¹ Please use the following typology: perfect competition; monopoly – one seller; oligopoly – few sellers; monopsony – one buyer; oligopsony – few buyers; other – describe.

¹² Please describe in terms of: symmetrical or asymmetrical – including high, medium or low asymmetry

<i>What digital infrastructure is available for practices at the processing stage of the VC ?</i>	-	-
<i>Please note any key aspects relating to infrastructure in that are important to understanding the processing stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>	-	
Strategies and vision		Scale (MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)
<i>What sectoral or VC-specific strategic plans or documents support actors and practices at the processing stage of the focal VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>What territorial strategies or visions (e.g. green recovery) have a direct relationship on function and performance at the processing stage of the focal VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>Please note any key aspects of these strategies and visions that are important to understanding the processing stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>	-	
Projects and programmes		Scale (MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)
<i>What sectoral or VC-specific projects or programmes support actors and practices at the processing stage of the focal VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>What other territorial projects or programmes have a direct influence on the function and</i>	-	-
	-	-

<i>performance at the processing stage of the focal VC ?</i>	-	-
<i>Please note any key aspects of these projects and programmes that are important to understanding the processing stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>	-	
	Regulatory	Scale <i>(MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)</i>
<i>What key legal and 'soft law' requirements do VC practices at the production stage have to comply with? (Think about health and safety, climate and environmental standards, licencing, employment law, taxation, property rights, legal contracts, etc)</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>Please note any key aspects of these regulatory institutions that are important to understanding the processing stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>	-	
	Cooperation	Scale <i>(MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)</i>
<i>What formal collective action institutions exist that support the processing stage of the VC? (Note, this does not include actors that are directly involved in the focal VC (included in actors section))</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>Please note any key aspects of these collective action institutions that are important to understanding the processing</i>		

<i>stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>		
	Finance	Scale <i>(MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)</i>
<i>How are practices at the processing stage of the VC financed ?</i>	-	
<i>Is access to capital and revenue a problem for actors at the processing stage of the VC? (If yes, please specify how)</i>	-	
<i>Is the processing stage of the VC associated with any 'new' private sector investment ? (Think about payment for eco-system services, carbon credits, etc)</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>What public subsidies or incentives are available to support actors and practices at the processing stage of the VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>What taxes or other levies are relevant to practices at the processing stage of the VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>What other fiscal charges (interest rates, exchange rates) impact on the processing stage of the VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>In what ways does the land market and price of land impact on the processing stage of the VC?</i>	-	
<i>Please note any key aspects of these financial institutions that are important to understanding the processing stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>	-	
	Certification processes	Scale <i>(MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)</i>

<p>What regional and/or quality assurance processes are relevant to the processing stage of the VC?</p> <p>(Include, PDO, PGI, etc.)</p>	-	-	-
	-	-	-
	-	-	-
<p>What other certification processes are relevant to the processing stage of the VC?</p>	-	-	-
	-	-	-
	-	-	-
<p>Please note any key aspects of these certification institutions that are important to understanding the processing stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</p>	-		
<p>Knowledge, advice and skills</p> <p>*Note informal knowledge sharing between VC actors is included in SC valorisation*</p>			<p>Scale</p> <p>(MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)</p>
<p>What specific training and skills provision is available for practices at the processing stage of the VC?</p>	-	-	-
	-	-	-
	-	-	-
<p>What knowledge advisors are available to support practices at the processing stage of the VC?</p>	-	-	-
	-	-	-
	-	-	-
<p>Please note any key aspects of these certification institutions that are important to understanding the processing stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</p>	-		
<p>Market structure</p>			<p>Scale</p> <p>(MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)</p>
	<p>Practice¹³</p>	<p>Market structure¹⁴</p>	<p>Power relations¹⁵</p>
<p>How would you describe the market structure and power relations within it for each practice</p>			-

¹³ This refers to different practices within the processing stage (identified in Table 1)

¹⁴ Please use the following typology : perfect competition; monopoly – one seller; oligopoly – few sellers; monopsony – one buyer; oligopsony – few buyers; other – describe.

¹⁵ Please describe in terms of: symmetrical or asymmetrical – including high, medium or low asymmetry

at the processing stage of the VC process? <i>(Please use the typologies outlined in footnotes)</i>				-
				-
Please note any key aspects relating to market structure institutions that are important to understanding the processing stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes	-			-
<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this table</u>				

c) Please reflect on different elements of the conducive enabling environment supporting practices and actors at the distribution & marketing stage of the VC in Table 16.

Table 16: Conducive enabling environment relevant to the distribution & marketing stage of the focal VC

	Infrastructure	Scale <i>(MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)</i>
What physical infrastructure (including transport & energy) is available for practices at the distribution & marketing stage of the VC?	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
What digital infrastructure is available for practices at the production stage of the VC ?	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
Please note any key aspects relating to infrastructure in that are important to understanding the distribution & marketing stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes	-	

Strategies and vision		Scale (MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)
<i>What sectoral or VC-specific strategic plans or documents support actors and practices at the distribution & marketing stage of the focal VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>What territorial strategies or visions (e.g. green recovery) have a direct relationship on function and performance at the distribution & marketing stage of the focal VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>Please note any key aspects of these strategies and visions that are important to understanding the distribution & marketing stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>	-	
Projects and programmes		Scale (MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)
<i>What sectoral or VC-specific projects or programmes support actors and practices at the distribution & marketing stage of the focal VC ?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>What other territorial projects or programmes have a direct influence on the function and performance at the distribution & marketing stage of the focal VC ?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>Please note any key aspects of these projects and programmes that are important to understanding the distribution & marketing stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it</i>	-	

<i>contributes to generating outcomes</i>		
Regulatory		Scale <i>(MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)</i>
<i>What key legal and 'soft law' requirements do VC practices at the distribution & marketing stage have to comply with? (Think about health and safety, climate and environmental standards, licencing, employment law, taxation, property rights, legal contracts, etc)</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>Please note any key aspects of these regulatory institutions that are important to understanding the distribution & marketing stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>	-	
Cooperation		Scale <i>(MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)</i>
<i>What formal collective action institutions exist that support the distribution & marketing stage of the VC? (Note, this does not include actors that are directly involved in the focal VC (included in actors section))</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>Please note any key aspects of these collective action institutions that are important to understanding the distribution & marketing stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>		
Finance		Scale

		(MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)
<i>How are practices at the distribution & marketing stage of the VC financed ?</i>	-	
<i>Is access to capital and revenue a problem for actors at the distribution & marketing stage of the VC? (If yes, please specify how)</i>	-	
<i>Is the distribution & marketing stage of the VC associated with any 'new' private sector investment ? (Think about payment for eco-system services, carbon credits, etc)</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>What public subsidies or incentives are available to support actors and practices at the distribution & marketing stage of the VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>What taxes or other levies are relevant to practices at the distribution & marketing stage of the VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>What other fiscal charges (interest rates, exchange rates) impact on the distribution & marketing stage of the VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>In what ways does the land market and price of land impact on the distribution & marketing stage of the VC?</i>	-	
<i>Please note any key aspects of these financial institutions that are important to understanding the distribution & marketing stage of the VC; its role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>	-	
Certification processes		Scale (MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)
	-	-

<i>What regional and/or quality assurance processes are relevant to the distribution & marketing stage of the VC?</i> <i>(Include, PDO, PGI, etc.)</i>	-			-
	-			-
<i>What other certification processes are relevant to the distribution & marketing stage of the VC?</i>	-			-
	-			-
	-			-
<i>Please note any key aspects of these certification institutions that are important to understanding the distribution & marketing stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>	-			
Knowledge, advice and skills <i>*Note informal knowledge sharing between VC actors is included in SC valorisation*</i>				Scale <i>(MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)</i>
<i>What specific training and skills provision is available for practices at the distribution & marketing stage of the VC?</i>	-			-
	-			-
	-			-
<i>What knowledge advisors are available to support practices at the distribution & marketing stage of the VC?</i>	-			-
	-			-
	-			-
<i>Please note any key aspects of these certification institutions that are important to understanding the distribution & marketing stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>	-			
Market structure				Scale <i>(MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)</i>
	<i>Practice¹⁶</i>	<i>Market structure¹⁷</i>	<i>Power relations¹⁸</i>	
<i>How would you describe the market structure and power relations within it for each practice</i>				-

¹⁶ This refers to different practices within the distribution & marketing stage (identified in Table 1)

¹⁷ Please use the following typology : perfect competition; monopoly – one seller; oligopoly – few sellers; monopsony – one buyer; oligopsony – few buyers; other – describe.

¹⁸ Please describe in terms of: symmetrical or asymmetrical – including high, medium or low asymmetry

at the production stage of the VC process? (Please use the typologies outlined in footnotes)				-
				-
Please note any key aspects relating to market structure institutions that are important to understanding the distribution & marketing stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes	-			-
<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this table</u>				

d) Please reflect on different elements of the conducive enabling environment supporting practices and actors at the consumption stage of the VC in Table 17.

Table 17: Conducive enabling environment relevant to the consumption stage of the focal VC

Infrastructure		Scale (MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)
What physical infrastructure is available for practices at the consumption stage of the VC?	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
What digital infrastructure is available for practices at the consumption stage of the VC ?	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
Please note any key aspects relating to infrastructure in that are important to understanding the consumption stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes	-	
Strategies and vision		Scale (MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)

<i>What sectoral or VC-specific strategic plans or documents support actors and practices at the consumption stage of the focal VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>What territorial strategies or visions (e.g., green recovery) have a direct relationship on function and performance at the consumption stage of the focal VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>Please note any key aspects of these strategies and visions that are important to understanding the consumption stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>	-	
Projects and programmes		Scale <i>(MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)</i>
<i>What sectoral or VC-specific projects or programmes support actors and practices at the consumption stage of the focal VC ?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>What other territorial projects or programmes have a direct influence on the function and performance at the consumption stage of the focal VC ?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>Please note any key aspects of these projects and programmes that are important to understanding the consumption stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>	-	
Regulatory		Scale

		(MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)
<p><i>What key legal and ‘soft law’ requirements do VC practices at the consumption stage have to comply with?</i></p> <p><i>(Think about health and safety, climate and environmental standards, licencing, employment law, taxation, property rights, legal contracts, etc)</i></p>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<p><i>Please note any key aspects of these regulatory institutions that are important to understanding the consumption stage of the VC; it’s role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i></p>	-	
Cooperation		Scale (MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)
<p><i>What formal collective action institutions exist that support the consumption stage of the VC?</i></p> <p><i>(Note, this does not include actors that are directly involved in the focal VC (included in actors section))</i></p>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<p><i>Please note any key aspects of these collective action institutions that are important to understanding the consumption stage of the VC; it’s role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i></p>		
Finance		Scale (MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)
<p><i>How are practices at the consumption stage of the VC financed?</i></p>	-	

<i>Is access to capital and revenue a problem for actors at the consumption stage of the VC? (If yes, please specify how)</i>	-	
<i>Is the consumption stage of the VC associated with any 'new' private sector investment ? (Think about payment for eco-system services, carbon credits, etc)</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>What public subsidies or incentives are available to support actors and practices at the production stage of the VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>What taxes or other levies are relevant to practices at the consumption stage of the VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>What other fiscal charges (interest rates, exchange rates) impact on the consumption stage of the VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>In what ways does the land market and price of land impact on the consumption stage of the VC?</i>	-	
<i>Please note any key aspects of these financial institutions that are important to understanding the consumption stage of the VC; it's role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>	-	
Certification processes		Scale (MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)
<i>What regional and/or quality assurance processes are relevant to the consumption stage of the VC? (Include, PDO, PGI, etc.)</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>What other certification processes are relevant to the consumption stage of the VC?</i>	-	-
	-	-
	-	-
<i>Please note any key aspects of these certification institutions that are important to understanding</i>	-	

<i>the consumption stage of the VC; its role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>				
Knowledge, advice and skills				Scale
Note informal knowledge sharing between VC actors is included in SC valorisation				(MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)
<i>What specific training and skills provision is available for practices at the consumption stage of the VC?</i>	-			-
	-			-
	-			-
<i>What knowledge advisors are available to support practices at the consumption stage of the VC?</i>	-			-
	-			-
	-			-
<i>Please note any key aspects of these certification institutions that are important to understanding the consumption stage of the VC; its role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>		-		
Market structure				Scale
	<i>Practice¹⁹</i>	<i>Market structure²⁰</i>	<i>Power relations²¹</i>	(MRL, MRR, national, EU/international)
<i>How would you describe the market structure and power relations within it for each consumption at the production stage of the VC process? (Please use the typologies outlined in footnotes)</i>				-
				-
				-
<i>Please note any key aspects relating to market structure institutions that are important to understanding the consumption stage of the VC; its role in the VC process; and how it contributes to generating outcomes</i>		-		

¹⁹ This refers to different practices within the consumption stage (identified in Table 1)

²⁰ Please use the following typology : perfect competition; monopoly – one seller; oligopoly – few sellers; monopsony – one buyer; oligopsony – few buyers; other – describe.

²¹ Please describe in terms of: symmetrical or asymmetrical – including high, medium or low asymmetry

Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this table

- e) **Finally, please comment on the overall governance system for the MRL.** Consider hierarchy, markets, networks, and communities. What does this governance style tell us about the current structure of the VC and how it is generating outcomes? What, if any, are the territorial governance conflicts that effect the VC?

Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section

4. Spatial Analysis and Telecoupling (Step 6)

- a) **Please name the units of analysis in Table 18, including how they relate to EC nomenclature.**

Table 18: Spatial units of analysis

<u>MRL</u>	-
<u>MRR</u>	-
<u>Nation or Member State</u>	-

<u>International (global or EU)</u>	-
<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>	

b) For each practice stage, please note the proportion²² of practices taking place in each of the four spatial units in Table 19. You may also want to consider each practice stage in terms of the EU rural -urban typology²³

Table 19: Proportion of Practices in space

	Production	Processing	Distribution & Marketing	Consumption
<u>MRL</u>				
<u>MRR</u>				
<u>Nation/ Member State</u>				
<u>International</u>				
<i>Optional: Rural-urban typology</i>				
<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>				

²² <25%, 25-50% 51-75% >75%

²³ Predominately urban, intermediate, predominately rural (see Section 3.5 of the Methodological Guidelines for WP4 document for more information)

c) For each practice stage, please note the proportion²⁴ of actors involved in each of the spatial units in Table 20. You may also want to consider each actor type stage in terms of the EU rural -urban typology²⁵

Table 20: Proportion of VC actors in space

Spatial unit	MRL	MRR	Nation	International	Optional: Rural-urban typology
Actor type					
<u>LUS manager</u>					
<u>NGO</u>					
<u>Civil society</u>					
<u>Broker/advisor.</u>					
<u>Business (agri)</u>					
<u>Business (non-agri)</u>					
<u>Public sector</u>					
<u>Research</u>					
<u>Other</u>					
Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section					

d) In the space below, please consider where different consumers markets for your focal VC are based. If dealing with a global VC, note the main ports associated with the import/export and the main export markets.

²⁴ <25%, 25-50%, 51-75%, >75%

²⁵ Predominately urban, intermediate, predominately rural (see Section 3.5 of the Methodological Guidelines for WP4 document for more information)

Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section

e) For each practice stage, please note the proportion²⁶ of the economic (Table 21), socio-cultural (Table 22), and environmental (Table 23) values/outcomes²⁷ accrued across each of the spatial units.

Table 21: Proportion of economic values/outcomes accrued in different spatial units

	Production	Processing	Distribution & Marketing	Consumption
<u>MRL</u>				
<u>MRR</u>				
<u>Nation/ Member State</u>				
<u>International</u>				
<i>Optional: Rural-urban typology</i>				
Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section				

Table 22: Proportion of socio-cultural values/outcomes accrued in different spatial units

	Production	Processing	Distribution & Marketing	Consumption

²⁶ <25%, 25-50%, 51-75%, >75%

²⁷ Identified in Section 3.3.4

<u>MRL</u>				
<u>MRR</u>				
<u>Nation/ Member State</u>				
<u>International</u>				
<i>Optional: Rural-urban typology</i>				
<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>				

Table 23: Proportion of environmental values/outcomes accrued in different spatial units

	Production	Processing	Distribution & Marketing	Consumption
<u>MRL</u>				
<u>MRR</u>				
<u>Nation/ Member State</u>				
<u>International</u>				
<i>Optional: Rural-urban typology</i>				
<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>				

- f) In the space below, please consider if tele-coupling in your focal VC involves flows entering or leaving the MRL. Please also consider spill-over flows (a node in a network between sender and receiver) and note where the other socio-ecological systems are located.

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Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section

5. Interactions with other VCs (Assemblage) (Step 7)

- a) In the space below, please note 1-2 additional VCs that have important interactions with your focal VC and why have they been selected:

Additional VC1

Additional VC2 (if appropriate)

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Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section

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- b) **What are the final product(s) associated with the additional VCs you have selected?**
Think about the different value propositions associated with the product and also include information about different categories of the final product (for example, premium or discount varieties)

Additional VC1

Additional VC2 (if appropriate)
<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>

c) How long have these additional VCs existed in the MRL?

Additional VC1
Additional VC2 (if appropriate)
<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>

d) Please note all the relevant practices at each stage of your additional VC(s) using the Table 24.

Table 24: Practices involved in additional VC(s)

Practice type	Additional VC	List of practices
<u>Production</u> <i>Think about all the practices involved in <u>production of commodities</u> on which the final product(s) are based.</i>	VC1 : [name]	-
	VC2 : [name]	-
<u>Processing</u>	VC1 : [name]	-

<i>Think about all the activities which involve <u>transformation of commodities</u> into the final product(s).</i>	VC2 : [name]	-
<u>Distribution and Marketing</u> <i>Think about practices relevant to <u>how the product is provided to the consumer.</u></i>	VC1 : [name]	-
	VC2 : [name]	-
<u>Consumption</u> <i>Think about practices relevant to <u>consumption of the end product(s).</u></i>	VC1 : [name]	-
	VC2 : [name]	-
<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>		

e) In the space below, please consider whether the same practices generate the assemblage, or does the assemblage require adaptation from original practices in the focal VC?

Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section

f) Please highlight the territorial capitals enrolled in each stage of your additional VC(s) using Table 25:

Table 25: Territorial capitals involved in additional VC(s)

Practice type	Additional VC	Economic capital	Socio-cultural capital	Environmental capital
<u>Production</u> Think about all the practices involved in <u>production of commodities</u> on which the final product(s) are based.	VC1 : [name]	-	-	-
	VC2 : [name]	-	-	-
<u>Processing</u> Think about all the activities which involve <u>transformation of commodities</u> into the final product(s).	VC1 : [name]	-	-	-
	VC2 : [name]	-	-	-
<u>Distribution and Marketing</u> Think about practices relevant to <u>how the product is provided to the consumer</u> .	VC1 : [name]	-	-	-
	VC2 : [name]	-	-	-
<u>Consumption</u> Think about practices relevant to <u>consumption of the end product(s)</u> .	VC1 : [name]	-	-	-
	VC2 : [name]	-	-	-
Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section				

- g) **What common territorial capitals are involved in the assemblage between the focal and additional VCs?**

Additional VC1
Additional VC2 (if appropriate)
<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>

h) Please note all the actors involved in your additional VC(s) using Table 26.

Table 26: Actors in additional VC(s)

Actor type	Additional VC	List of actors
<u>LUS manager</u>	VC1 : [name]	
	VC2 : [name]	
<u>NGO</u>	VC1 : [name]	
	VC2 : [name]	
<u>Civil society</u>	VC1 : [name]	
	VC2 : [name]	
<u>Broker/advisor</u>	VC1 : [name]	
	VC2 : [name]	
<u>Business (agri)</u>	VC1 : [name]	
	VC2 : [name]	
<u>Business (non-agri)</u>	VC1 : [name]	
	VC2 : [name]	
<u>Public sector</u>	VC1 : [name]	

	VC2 : [name]	
Research	VC1 : [name]	
	VC2 : [name]	
Other	VC1 : [name]	
	VC2 : [name]	
<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>		

i) In the space below, please consider whether assemblage with additional VCs involves new actors not involved in the focal VC?

Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section

j) In Table 27, please consider the flows that move between your focal VC and additional VC(s). In each appropriate cell provide a short narrative indicating the direction of flows²⁸ and any other relevant information

Table 27: Flows between VCs

	Focal VC	Additional VC1 [name]	Additional VC2 [name]
<u>Flows – materials</u>			
<u>Flows – information</u>			

²⁸ From FVC to AVC; From AVC to FVC; Bi-directional

<u>Flows - finance</u>			
<u>By-products</u>			
<u>Externalities</u>			
<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>			

k) In Table 28, please consider whether (and how) the assemblage influences outcomes in the focal VC.

Table 28: Affect of assemblage on focal VC outcomes

	Economic	Socio-Cultural	Environmental
<u>Amplifies +ve</u>			
<u>Counteract -ve</u>			
<u>No affect</u>			
<u>Counteract +ve</u>			
<u>Amplifies -ve</u>			
<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>			

l) What additional supporting infrastructure or institutions are involved in the assemblage?

Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section

m) In Table 29, please note what proportions of the assemblage exist within the MRL, and what proportions are located in other regions, nations/memberstates, or international space?

Table 29: Proportions of assemblage across space

	MRL	MRR	Nation	International
<u>Assemblage Practices</u>				
<u>Assemblage Actors</u>				
<u>Assemblage Outcomes</u>				
<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>				

n) In the space below, please consider where there are synergies, and conflicts or problems in the assemblage between VCs.

Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section

6. Consideration for Further Tasks

a) What would you like to remember or explore further in T4.3 interviews ?

<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>

b) What might you want to focus on for the T4.4 workshop on current performance of the VC assemblage ?

<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>

c) What issues regarding sustainability, vulnerability and resilience seem relevant for T4.5 ? Also consider, how can local assets be mobilized into relational configurations with networks to build resilient and sustainable value chains? (including green recovery, C19 recovery)?

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<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>

d) What strategies can improve the resilience and sustainability of value chains? (T4.6)

<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>

e) Please also note any other data or observations that might be useful to WP5 (clustering); WP6 (foresight) or WP7 (policy).

<u>Please use this space to keep track of the sources referred to for this section</u>

7. Compiled reference list

Please use this section to alphabetically compile references recorded in individual sections of the report in the style shown in Table 30. We are grateful for careful completion of this list in support of Deliverable reporting.

Table 30: Referencing style to be adopted

<p>Brunori, G., Avermaete, T., Bartolini, F., Brzezina, N., Marsden, T., Mathijs, E., Moragues-Faus, A., & Sonnino, R. (2020). The Vulnerability of Food Systems. In <i>Innovation for Sustainability</i>. Emerald Publishing Limited.</p> <p>Delgado-Serrano, M. D. M., & Ramos, P. (2015). Making Ostrom’s framework applicable to characterise social ecological systems at the local level. <i>International Journal of the Commons</i>, 9(2), 808. https://doi.org/10.18352/ijc.56.</p> <p>TEEB (2018) <i>TEEB for Agriculture & Food: Scientific and Economic Foundations</i>. Geneva: UN Environment> Available at: http://teebweb.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/Foundations_Report_Final_October.pdf</p>

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MOVING

MOUNTAIN VALORIZATION THROUGH
INTERCONNECTEDNESS AND GREEN GROWTH

